
THE FORMATION AND THE DEVELOPMENT OF PRAGMALINGUISTICS

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.8012750>

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Annotation.

This article gives information about the history of pragmalinguistics and its further development.

Keywords.

pragmatics, pragmalinguistics, speech acts, discourse, communication.

We all speak different languages. But we are united in the fundamental ability to put words together in a certain order, to use the language according to the situation, and to pronounce corresponding replicas. The only difference between us is that each language has its own pragmatic rules that determine the adequacy of the use of linguistic means according to the communicative situation. Thus, the success of communication depends largely on the knowledge of these pragmatic rules, that is, from the presence of pragmatic competence.

Mention of pragmatic competence first appeared in Canal, where it appears under the guise of sociolinguistic competence (knowledge of contextually relevant language use). This understanding of competence bears some resemblance to a sociopragmatic component of Leach, which includes "the interlocutor's knowledge of pragmatic conventions and the ability to understand the context of the situation and language intentions" [1,54]. But it was Bachman who singled out the concept of "pragmatic competence" as a separate concept [2,10]. Bachman presented a model of communicative language ability, which consists of three elements, such as language competence, strategic competence, and physiological mechanisms.

Language competence is divided, in turn, into pragmatic competence and organizational competence. Pragmatic competence, in turn, breaks down into illocutionary competence (knowledge of speech acts and language functions) and

sociolinguistic competence (understanding the contextual correspondence of linguistic forms that implement illocution).

The division between illocutionary and sociolinguistic is similar to how Leach and Thomas divided pragmatics into pragmatolinguistics and sociopragmatics. Thus, pragmatolinguistic competence is knowledge about the linguistic resources that exist in a given language for the implementation [1,3]

The word pragmatics comes from the Greek word "work", and the name of the science itself testifies that its subject matter is "language in action", in living functioning. The Greek historian Polybius (d. 118 BC) at one time called his writings pragmatic, because he believed that they were intended to educate readers and be useful to them. In philosophy and psychology, this term was used in the meaning of experience, activity. After C. Peirce and C. Morris, pragmatics is also called the attitude of the user to the signs he uses, and the corresponding section of semiotics.

Linguistic pragmatics is a discipline that studies language not in itself and for itself, but as a means used by a person in his activity. Today, pragmatics is an interdisciplinary field in which almost all linguistic, many logical-philosophical, sociological, psychological, ethnographic and some cybernetic (associated with the creation of artificial intelligence) areas are involved. The empirical tasks of the general theory of pragmatics include the development of a cognitive model for the production, understanding, memorization of speech acts, as well as a model of communicative interaction and the use of language in specific sociocultural situations. [3,29]

A unified scientific definition of pragmatics as a science has not yet developed, however, there is no doubt that it was formed under the influence of a linguistic paradigm focused on the study of speech communication.

The idea of the need to take into account the "human factor" in linguistic research was formed in semiotics. Semiotics (from the Greek "sign") is a scientific discipline that studies what is common in the structure and functioning of various sign (semiotic) systems that store and transmit information, whether they are systems operating in human society, in nature or in man himself.

In the first works on semiotics, which aimed to study the structure of a sign situation in a dynamic, procedural aspect, including the participants in this situation, the concept of pragmatics appears. C.U. Morris (1938) distinguished three branches of semiotics: syntactics (or syntax) dealing with the relations between signs; semantics, which studies the relationship between the sign and the signified (designate), and pragmatics, which studies the relationship between the sign and its interpreter, i.e. those who create, accept and understand the sign. A great

contribution to the development of the ideas of formal pragmatics was made by R. Carnap.

According to T. van Dyck, who defines pragmatics as the study of "language in context", pragmatics is an integral component of linguistic theory, which has a status comparable to that of syntax and semantics.

In 1970, the International Symposium on the Pragmatics of Natural Languages was held. Its participants were unanimous that "the pragmatic aspects of communication in natural language (at least some of these aspects) should be studied within the framework of linguistic theory along with the semantic and syntactic aspects of this communication". [3,30]

The formation of linguistic pragmatics is directly related to changes in the general orientation of foreign linguistics that emerged in the early 1970s, which can be characterized as a transition from studying the language of a formal system, abstracted from the conditions of its use, to considering language as a means of communicative interaction taking place in a social context.

The question of the ratio of pragmatics and pragmalinguistics does not have an unambiguous solution. Some scientists consider pragmalinguistics to be a linguistic branch of pragmatics, whose task is to describe signs and their combinations in communications; others consider it as a "pragmatic component of the theory language", along with phonetics, semantics, syntax; others talk about "the primacy of the pragmatic component linguistics". There are also such scientists for whom the terms "pragmalinguistics", "pragmatics" and "text theory" are equivalent. The contradictory understanding of the subject of pragmalinguistics is primarily due to a complex history formation of pragmatics [1,4].

Pragmalinguistics stands out as a field of linguistic studies, having as its object the relationship between linguistic units and the conditions of their use in a certain communicative-pragmatic space in which the speaker/writer and listener/reader interact and for characteristics of which are important specific indications of the place and time of their speech interactions associated with the act of communicating goals and expectations. Also, it is defined as the science that deals with the selection of the most optimal of the means available in the language for the most successful impact on the listener or reader, to effectively achieve the intended goal in the specific circumstances of verbal communication.

The central concept of linguistic pragmatics and the main unit of study in the theory of speech acts, the foundations which were laid by J. Austin, is a speech act. The problem of speech acts and speech formation is also contained in the linguistic concepts of W. Humboldt, S. Balli, S. Kartsevsky, L. P. Yakubinsky, K. L. Buhler, E.

Benveniste, M. M. Bakhtin, and others, where the speech act is defined as a way for a person to achieve a certain goal or as a purposeful speech action performed by

with the principles and rules of speech behavior accepted in a given society. However, there is a growing body of research that directly the subject is not a separate abstract utterance, but the process of verbal communication itself, in which the utterance is considered an element of more large speech formations.

Object

research should not serve as individual speech acts embodied in the participants' replicas, but as speech roles, i.e., series speech acts of each of the participants in the communication episode. The speaker himself is proclaimed the subject of activity and communication, "the subject of linguistic communication, the creator of relationships with other interactants and communicants in this discourse"[1,4].

For linguistic pragmatics, explanation and description of the mechanism of human behavior to provide speech impact are also important tasks to your interlocutor. First place in pragmatic studies put forward a person as a subject of speech activity. Any statement is an independent sentence, a replica in a dialogue, or connected text - that relates to the speaker. In the process of verbal communication, the speaker does not act as a kind of idealized, global personality with all its inherent psychological and social characteristics, but as a person who reveals one or more of his social functions and psychological characteristics, depending on the specific conditions of communication.

Before the final separation of pragmalinguistics into an independent field of research, it was noted that pragmatics did not have clear contours, it was determined

as "a field of study in semiotics and linguistics, which studies the functioning of linguistic signs in speech". The questions that have been studied within its framework, include those related to speaking subject, addressee, their interaction in communication, and situation communication.

Gradually the interest of researchers moves from questions of functioning language to the issues of dependence of the functioning of language units on those who use the language. The need to illuminate the subject of pragmalinguistics is due to the complexity of the path that this discipline has taken, the plurality of approaches, and methodological, philosophical justifications.

Understanding the subject of pragmalinguistics is based on the consideration of pragmatics as a discipline that studies the relationship between signs and people who create, perceive, and interpret them. Pragmatics explores the signs in their

attitude towards those who by these signs operate, and language is a sign system. Therefore, it can be argued that pragmalinguistics deals with the study of linguistic signs in their relation to those who "create, receive and interpret these signs.

A wide range of problems falls into the area of interest of pragmalinguistics, which is not limited to the study of relationships in which linguistic the sign and its interpreters - the speaker and listening but touching learning influence of context and background knowledge on communicants, issues of choosing the optimal language means for the most effective impact of participants in speech communication, consideration of implementation speaker's intentions in speech acts.

There is another classification direction in pragmalinguistics: functional and hidden pragmalinguistics. Within the framework of functional pragmalinguistics, the speech activity of the sender of the text with a thoughtful deliberate choice of illocutions is studied, and the latent pragmalinguistics explores the intuitive habitual choice of speech signals actualization of the speech behavior of the sender of the text. Such a division makes sense, of course, only for research purposes, and yet it is useful, as it leads to important practical results. Numerous studies are currently underway in hidden pragmalinguistics. For example, the personal qualities of representatives of various social groups are studied; pragmalinguistic features of various linguistic units are revealed; the features of the speech behavior of the authors of texts of various communicative orientations are considered; determined national and cultural specificity of communicants.

Research within the framework of the theory of speech genres are devoted to the study of sustainable forms of speech and features of speech behavior, description of speech actions by the type of reality, highlighting the stylistic aspect as an element of the genre unity of the statement. A common feature of a speech act and a speech genre is also the dynamic aspect: the study of these components in the process of constructing the text, and the dynamics of the dialogue.

In conclusion, linguistic pragmatics is a branch of linguistics that studies the use of language in the communicative process. The pragmatic function of language is the presence of a goal to influence the interlocutor through messages of this information and it is considered one of the main functions of the language. In this regard, pragmalinguistics can be defined as the linguistics of the direct regulation of human behavior. The main task of pragmalinguistics becomes the study of a language in its pragmatic function.

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